

Application form: Open Science Infrastructure (2024) - Pre-proposal

Section 1 – Applicant(s)

Name of the main applicant	<i>Prof. Dr. Ludo Waltman</i>
Affiliation – institution	<i>Leiden University</i>
Affiliation – department	<i>Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS)</i>
Position	<i>Full Professor and Scientific Director</i>
End date of contract	<i>Permanent position</i>
E-mail address	<i>waltmanlr@cwts.leidenuniv.nl</i>
ORCID ID	<i>https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8249-1752</i>

Name of the co-applicant	<i>Dr. Irene Nooren</i>
Affiliation – institution	<i>SURF</i>
Affiliation – department	<i>Innovation</i>
Position	<i>Innovation Program Manager</i>
End date of contract	<i>Permanent position</i>
E-mail address	<i>irene.nooren@surf.nl</i>
ORCID ID	<i>https://orcid.org/0009-0006-7789-9140</i>

Name of the co-applicant	<i>Nienke Annemiek van Schaverbeke</i>
Affiliation – institution	<i>TU Delft (Library)</i>
Affiliation – department	<i>TU Delft Library, Research Services, Scholarly Communications and Publishing</i>
Position	<i>Head of Scholarly Communications and Publishing, Publishing Director TU Delft Open Publishing</i>
End date of contract	<i>Permanent position</i>
E-mail address	<i>n.a.vanschaverbeke@tudelft.nl</i>
ORCID ID	

Name of the co-applicant	<i>Anna van 't Veer</i>
Affiliation – institution	<i>Leiden University</i>
Affiliation – department	<i>Institute of Psychology</i>
Position	<i>Assistant Professor</i>
End date of contract	<i>Permanent position</i>
E-mail address	<i>a.e.van.t.veer@fsw.leidenuniv.nl</i>
ORCID ID	<i>https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2733-1841</i>

Section 2 - Summary

Proposed project title	<i>Next-generation publishing: Advancing the publish-review-curate model</i>
Project type	<i>Large</i>
Project duration (in months)	<i>48</i>

Section 3 – Project description

3.1 Alignment of your project with the aim of the call

The traditional journal publishing model is widely criticized for being non-transparent, slow, and inefficient. The [publish-review-curate \(PRC\) model](#) offers a more transparent, more rapid, and more efficient approach to scientific publishing. In this model, articles are published in a repository before undergoing peer review, thereby accelerating the dissemination of new scientific knowledge. Peer review takes place openly. Review reports and by choice reviewer identities are published alongside an article, making peer review more transparent (anyone can access the reviews) and more efficient (reviews can be used and reused not only by authors and journals editors but also by the readers of an article). In the curation phase, an editorial assessment is made of the quality and/or relevance of an article. This offers an efficient way for readers to decide whether an article is trustworthy or whether it is likely to be of interest to them.

There is a growing interest in the PRC model, both in the Netherlands and internationally. In the [NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda](#), the objective is that PRC will be the norm by 2030. Likewise, the [Towards Responsible Publishing proposal](#) of cOAlition S, a group of research funders including the Dutch Research Council (NWO), starts from the idea that articles must be shared immediately and openly and reviews must be published. PRC is mentioned as a model for realizing these goals. PRC is also promoted by the European Commission through [Open Research Europe](#).

In a [recent survey](#), more than 50% of the Dutch respondents indicated to be in support of publishing models like PRC, and less than 25% indicated to be opposed. Likewise, in a [recent petition](#), hundreds of Dutch researchers supported “open source institutional repositories, diamond platforms, preprint servers, innovations in community peer reviewing, and thematic curation”. Despite this, the PRC adoption in the Netherlands is still low. In 2023, only about 500 articles with Dutch authors adopted PRC.

The strong in-principle support for PRC combined with the low level of actual adoption suggests significant practical barriers prevent Dutch researchers from adopting the model. To help overcome these barriers, **the goal of our project is to set up PRC journals/platforms for at least ten Dutch research communities**. We will use the insights we obtain into potential problems and areas of improvement and translate these into requirements for large-scale PRC adoption in the Netherlands.

Rather than building new infrastructure from scratch, we will as much as possible build on existing infrastructures (e.g., eLife/Kotahi, PKP/OJS, SciPost, Peer Community In) and adapt them to the needs of Dutch research communities interested in adopting PRC. Like traditional journals, PRC platforms are in many cases discipline specific (e.g., life sciences, physics, humanities), raising the need for interoperability of publication infrastructures.

3.2 Project plan

To realize the overarching goal of the project, activities will be developed in four work packages.

Work package 1 – Coordination and community engagement

Goal: To identify research communities in the Netherlands interested in adopting PRC-like publishing models and to coordinate with related initiatives in the Netherlands. Expected outcomes:

- Community of practice of researchers, librarians, publishers, policy makers, and others interested in promoting PRC in the Netherlands, working closely together with Open Science Communities NL
- Identification of at least ten research communities in the Netherlands across all scientific disciplines that are interested in adopting PRC, for instance communities that are currently running a diamond OA journal or a journal published by a commercial publisher
- Exploration of sustainable business models for community-led scientific publishing, in coordination with diamond OA initiatives working on developing sustainable models
- Exploration of, and coordination with the UKB working groups such as Open Access and Research Support to embed PRC journals/platforms in institutional OA policies and catalogues

Work package 2 – Strengthening infrastructures to meet community needs

Goal: To ensure the availability of infrastructures meets the core needs of research communities in the Netherlands interested in adopting PRC-like publishing models. Expected outcomes:

- Analysis of the publishing needs of the research communities identified in WP1

- Analysis of the functionalities offered by existing infrastructures that may be used to run PRC journals/platforms, such as institutional repositories, preprint servers, and systems for managing peer review (e.g., Kotahi, OJS, and SciPost)
- Analysis of gaps in the functionalities of existing infrastructures that need to be filled to meet the core needs of the research communities identified in WP1
- Enhanced infrastructures that meet the core needs of the research communities identified in WP1

Work package 3 – Strengthening interoperability of infrastructures

Goal: To ensure PRC infrastructures are interoperable and easy to use in the workflow of researchers. Expected outcomes:

- A domain architecture for publication workflows, including a mapping of core infrastructure services (e.g., repositories and peer review platforms) and agreement on technical standards. It will be based on architectures such as HOSA (Higher Education Sector Architecture) in coalition with UKB and UNL
- Connect with the developments in the Open Research Information Agenda in the Netherlands and with relevant international initiatives (e.g., COAR Notify based on ActivityPub, Crossref, Society and Open Research Europe) to ensure alignment with partnering initiatives and increase their discoverability.
- Build an innovation community to work on improving software like OJS and Kotahi by adding the peer review and PRC functionalities identified in WP2.
- Improve user experience of PRC workflow, e.g., single sign on for researchers engaging with different publication workflow components (e.g., repositories and peer review platforms).

Work package 4 – Support and training

Goal: To provide support to research communities in the Netherlands interested in adopting PRC. Expected outcomes:

- Support for the research communities identified in WP1 to help them set up new PRC journals/platforms using the infrastructures identified and enhanced in WP2
- Training program for the research communities identified in WP1 to facilitate the adoption and use of new PRC journals/platforms
- Knowledge base to support research communities that want to adopt PRC

3.3 Team composition

Our team consists of the following organizations:

- **Leiden University.** Leiden University's Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) has led the creation of the [MetaROR \(MetaResearch Open Review\) PRC platform](#). In this project, it will lead WP2 and contribute to the other work packages. Leiden University will also contribute to community engagement and support (WP1, WP4).
- **SURF.** SURF is the Dutch ICT cooperative of education and research institutions. It has profound expertise on publication platforms such as Publinova and Edusources. SURF will lead WP3 and contribute to the other work packages.
- **TU Delft OPEN Publishing (TUDOP).** TUDOP, TU Delft's diamond OA publishing house, will use its PRC experience (The Evolving Scholar) to contribute to community engagement and support (WP1, WP4).
- **Utrecht University Library.** Will contribute to community engagement and support (WP1, WP4).
- **Open Science Communities Netherlands (OSC NL).** OSC NL will bring the opportunities of the PRC model to the attention of research communities in the Netherlands.

We will closely collaborate with cooperation partners:

- **Openjournals.** Openjournals, a diamond OA publishing platform for peer-reviewed journals, will bring the opportunities of the PRC model to the attention of the research communities it serves (WP1).
- **eLife.** eLife runs the world's most successful PRC journal. It also provides infrastructure for PRC journals/platforms. eLife will share its experience with PRC by contributing to WP4.

We envision developing partnerships with infrastructure organizations such as Coko/Kotahi and PKP/OJS and subcontracting technical work to them.

We plan to work together with the DURF (Dutch Repository Federation) and 'Infrastructures for Diamond Open Access' on implementing interoperability standards like event-notifications, metadata, licensing specifications and preprint functionality of repositories, and sustainable models for community-led publishing.

Section 4 – Budget

Type of costs	Short explanation	Costs
<i>Personnel costs</i>	0,8 FTE - Project manager	
	0,7 FTE - Community manager	
	0,25 FTE support by university libraries and OSC NL	
	0,2 FTE - software engineering	
	0,2 FTE - domain architect	
Total	2,15 FTE over 4 years	860.000 €
<i>Other costs</i>	Technical infrastructure improvement (contracted)	150.000 €
	Training, communication and travel costs	50.000 €
Total request from NWO		1.060.000 €

Section 5 – Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.